

RCSB PDB Task Tensorboard Results

1. Single Neuron model

1.1. Loss

1.2 PR_AUC

1.3 Bias Histogram

1.4 Weight Histogram

2. Model with 32 neurons

1.1. Loss

1.2 PR_AUC

1.3 Bias Histogram

1.4 Weight Histogram

3. Model with 64 Neurons

1.1. Loss

1.2 PR_AUC

PR_AUC for Fully Connected Model with 64 neurons

4. Model with 128 Neurons

1.1. Loss

1.2 PR_AUC

Bias histogram of models 3 and 4:

Weight histogram of models 3 and 4:

1.4 Weight Histogram

